

**BASIC SANITATION AND SCHOOLS: A CONTRIBUTION TO
ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN ABRAÃO-ILHA GRANDE-RJ,
BRAZIL**

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ABSTRACT

Deficiencies in wastewater treatment or the lack of treatment systems compromise accessibility to drinking water, resulting in health and environmental problems. Environmental education can be considered as one of the ways to raise awareness among the population and recognize their rights, ensuring information so that they can fight for better conditions and access to sanitation services. The objective of the study was to carry out a bibliographical survey on the different methodologies that address basic sanitation applied to schools in Brazil, for future implementation in schools in Vila de Abraão, Ilha Grande, south coast of the State of Rio de Janeiro. The methodological survey was carried out in the Google Scholar databases, and with

the data found, criteria listed in table form were established. The table served as an analysis tool considering the scenario in which the school found itself to select the most appropriate methodologies. In this way, the development of a tool to assist decision makers will allow the construction of a methodology suited to local and inclusive realities, aiming to establish dialogue between teachers, students and the community, for the development of a critical, broad vision. and developed on issues related to sanitation and local environmental preservation.

Keywords: environmental preservation; sanitation services; sewage treatment; colleges; Decision makers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The need to apply sustainability in the management of water resources is becoming more essential every day due to the levels of pollution in water bodies and their scarcity. Deficiency in wastewater treatment or the lack of treatment systems compromises accessibility to water, resulting in health and environmental problems. Such problems are generally also associated with the spread of diseases, mainly waterborne, caused by the lack of treatment and incorrect disposal of sewage. Where these affect not only the quality of life of a population, but also the water quality of water bodies, potentially causing ecological imbalances in associated ecosystems.

Sewage treatment is more than a fundamental item for protecting the environment and ensuring water availability; It is also a public health issue. Data taken from the Brazil Sanitation Panel (2018) indicate that in 2018, 115,151 hospitalizations of children up to 14 years old were recorded related to the lack of treated water and after contact with open sewage. These numbers represent around half of all hospitalizations recorded in public health units due to water transmission across the country.

According to chapter II of Law No. 9,795, which established the National Environmental Education Policy (BRASIL, 1999), Environmental Education is an integral, essential and permanent component of National Education, and must be present, in an articulated way, at the levels and modalities of Basic Education and Higher Education. To this end, educational institutions must promote it integrated into their institutional and pedagogical projects, promoting environmental awareness and the construction of values and virtues, in favor of its preservation.

In the context of health and sanitation, environmental education can be defined as a social practice that recommends not only the change of habits, practices and attitudes, but mainly the gradual change in the way of thinking, feeling and acting through the selection and

use of pedagogical methods. Therefore, educating and learning becomes a continuous process of collective, articulated and shared construction, as well as an incentive for the effective participation of local communities' resources (MOISÉS et al, 2010).

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2. METHODOLOGY

Vila de Abraão is located on Ilha Grande, district of Angra dos Reis, a municipality in the State of Rio de Janeiro. With approximately 3000 inhabitants, Vila de Abraão can be considered as the main gateway for tourism on the island, assuming the role of “economic capital”, being the place with the largest number of inns, restaurants, agencies and other services, of all island. It has sewage systems carried out by the Autonomous Water and Sewage Service (SAAE). However, the existing system only serves a part of the village's buildings. The other areas, not served by the network, have decentralized systems, consisting mainly of septic tank systems (or septic tanks) and sinks, poorly sized and without adequate or periodic maintenance. These facts become more evident when observing several places with irregular sewage disposal, bad odor throughout the village and a large amount of solid waste in water bodies (ILHA GRANDE, 2020).

The Brigadeiro Nóbrega Municipal School (EM Brigadeiro Nóbrega) is located in Vila do Abraão and receives students not only from Vila de Abraão, but also from other locations on the island, such as Dois Rios, Aroeira, Palmas, Saco do Céu, Praia de Fora, Parishes of Santana, Pouso, Lagoa Azul and Japariz. For this project, only students between the 6th and 9th year of Elementary School II were selected, with approximately 210 students. Furthermore, the school under study is part of the Mais Educação Program, created by the Ministry of Education, prioritizing state or municipal schools located in areas of social vulnerability. One of the pillars of the program is “Environmental education and sustainable society”, and its strategy is to integrate different knowledge, educational spaces, people from the community, diverse knowledge, seeking to articulate school knowledge with learning for life, for citizenship.

The methodological survey of environmental education focused on the area of sanitation was carried out through searches in the Google Scholar database, initially with the keywords: “Environmental Education”; "Basic sanitation"; “Schools” and “Brazil”, then the words “Rural

areas” were added; "Methodologies" and "Social technology". With this, published scientific articles were obtained that address the topic of environmental and health education in schools across Brazil. A specific selection of types of methodologies that have already been applied in different schools across Brazil was then carried out.

With the data obtained, inclusion criteria were established such as: (i) practical activities; (ii) use of open areas; (iii) use of auditorium; (iv) age group over 10 years old; (v) technological accessibility; and (vi) technical team specialized in the environmental area. These criteria were established to assist in the selection of the most suitable methodologies to be applied to the local realities of each school. In this way, the methodologies were classified according to compliance with the established criteria into three categories: **recommended** (100% of the criteria covered), **partially recommended** ($\geq 60\%$ of the criteria covered) and **not recommended** ($< 60\%$ of the criteria covered).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After surveying the articles published on the Google Scholar search site, the 6 most used or adopted methodologies in these studies were selected and evaluated, namely: Technical Visits; Practical Activities; Competitions/Scavenger hunts; Lectures and Seminars; Campaigns; and Games via mobile devices. Based on these methodologies, the inclusion criteria were applied to see which would be the most recommended for application in the Brigadeiro Nóbrega EM (Table 1).

Table 1: Comparative and classificatory evaluation of the selected methodologies with the theme of environmental and health education in schools in Brazil, to be applied to the current conditions of the Brigadeiro Nóbrega Municipal School, in Vila do Abraão, on Ilha Grande-RJ. The methodologies were classified as: recommended, partially recommended and not recommended. In blue, the parameters that meet the needs of the school studied are marked (Source: Authors)

Methodology	Practical part	Open Area	Auditorium	Age Range	Technological Accessibility	Technical Team	Selection
Technical visits	Necessary	Necessary	Not necessary	> 10 years	Not necessary	Biologist, Environmental Manager, Environmental/Health Engineer, Environmental Scientist	Recommended (100%)
Practical Activities	Necessary	Necessary	Not necessary	> 10 years	Not necessary	Biologist, Environmental Manager, Environmental/Health Engineer	Recommended (100%)

						alth Engineer, Environmental Scientist	
Competitions/Scavenger hunts	Necessa ry	Necessa ry	Not necessa ry	All ages	Not necessary	Biologist, Environmental Manager, Environmental/He alth Engineer, Environmental Scientist	Partially Recommen ded (83%)
Lectures and Seminars	Not necessar y	Not necessar y	Necessa ry	> 10 years	Not necessary	Biologist, Environmental Manager, Environmental/He alth Engineer, Environmental Scientist	Not Recommen ded (50%)
Campaigns	Not necessar y	Necessa ry	Not necessar y	All ages	Not necessary	Biologist, Environmental Manager, Environmental/He alth Engineer, Environmental Scientist	Partially Recommen ded (66%)
Games via mobile devices	Not necessar y	Not necessar y	Not necessar y	> 10 years	Necessary	Biologist, Environmental Manager, Environmental/He alth Engineer, Environmental Scientist	Not Recommen ded (50%)

After applying the criteria, those that met the conditions or that met the needs of EM Brigadeiro Nóbrega were marked in blue. Therefore, 2 methodologies were considered and classified as the most recommended to be applied in a second phase of the present study, namely: Technical Visits and Practical Activities. However, 2 others were partially recommended: Competitions/Scavenger Hunts and Campaigns, and 2 others were not recommended according to the needs and conditions established for the present study: Lectures and Seminars and Games via mobile devices. It is worth noting that this classification of the methodologies evaluated can be changed according to other conditions and needs found in other schools in Brazil and the present work did not aim to evaluate the methodology itself, but rather its applicability in the conditions established in the methodological outline of the present research. . Such selected methodologies will be evaluated in a second phase of the project.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that among the 6 methodologies researched and selected in the present study, only two met 100% of the criteria established for implementation at the Brigadeiro Nóbrega Municipal School, in Vila de Abraão on Ilha Grande, being classified as recommended: Technical Visits and Practical Activities .

Through this study, a methodology was established that can be used by decision makers as a tool to assist in choosing the most recommended pedagogical methodology to meet the needs and conditions presented in schools and to promote environmental and health education in young students from an early age. beginning of their training.

It is expected that the study will encourage the development of more environmental education actions, providing broad awareness among young people about the importance of caring for the environment, mainly related to health issues, as a fundamental tool for preserving public and environmental health. In addition to establishing dialogue between teachers, students and the community, to develop a critical, broad and developed view on issues related to sanitation and local environmental preservation.

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